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**NASOSLARNI BOSHQARISHDA MITSUBISHI
KONTROLLERLARIDAN FOYDALANISH**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada meliorativ yerlarda sug‘orishda oqovqa suvlarini ko‘tarish uchun uch fazali nasoslardan foydalanish hamda ularni masofadan turib boshqarishda PLC kontrollerlarini qo‘llash nazarda tutilgan. PLC kontrollerlariga nasosning ulanish sxemasi va uni boshqarish uchun dasturiy ta‘minot tizimini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: PLC kontroller, Mitsubishi, Nasos, Tadqiqot, Ladder.

Kirish. Yer osti va yer usti manbalaridan suv oluvchi inshootlar yiriklashib, suv tashish masofalari uzoqlashib, suv tozalash jarayonlari hamda inshootlari vujudga kelgan ekologik vaziyat va sharoitlar ta‘sirida murakkablashib bormoqda shu sababdan ham nasos — suyuqlikni bosim ostida so‘rish va haydash, gazlarni siqish yoki siyraklantirish, sochiluvchi jismlarni so‘rish va haydash uchun ishlatiladigan qurilma (gidravlik yoki pnevmatik mashina, apparat yoki asbob). Nasosning asosiy parametri — ma‘lum vaqt ichida (vaqt birligida) haydaladigan suv, gaz yoki havo miqdoriga teng ekanligidan hisoblanadi[1, 2, 3,, 4, 10, 12, 15,].

Material va usullar

Bu usulni o‘rganishga tayyorgarlik jarayonida bir qancha adabiyotlar, manbalar [6] o‘rganildi va tahlil qilindi, shunga o‘xshash turli xil materiallarning mosligi tekshirildi. Biroq nashrlar va tadqiqot natijalari qidiruv manbalarida uch fazali elektr motorning qulay usuli kamligini ko‘rsatdi. Bir tomondan bu usulning to‘liq dasturiy ta‘minoti nazariy asosining yo‘qligi bizni tadqiqot olib borishimizni qiyinlashtiradi. PLC dasturiy ta‘minot tizimida uch fazali elektr motorni boshqarish jarayoni keltirilgan bo‘lib ladder dastur tili orqali yoziladi. Sanoatda turli maqsadlarda ishlatiladigan ko‘plab motorlar va konveyerlar mavjud[13, 14, 15, 8].

XUSUSIYATLARI

<i>Dasturiy ta‘minot tili</i>	<i>Ladder</i>	
<i>Loyihani ishlab chiqish muhiti</i>	<i>GX 3</i>	
<i>Protessor moduli</i>	<i>DMK seriyali</i>	<i>FX3U</i>
<i>Dastur xotira bloki</i>	<i>STEPS RAM</i>	
<i>Dastur xotirasi</i>	<i>64 ming qadam</i>	
<i>bufer batareyasi</i>	<i>Ha</i>	
<i>Tsikl vaqti LD</i>	<i>65 ns</i>	
<i>MOV aylanish vaqti</i>	<i>642 ns</i>	
<i>RS-422 portlari soni</i>	<i>1</i>	

Diskret kirish kanallari soni
 Diskret kirish davri turi
 PLC bilan motorni boshqarish

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 Manba, iste'molchi

MUAMMO YECHIMI

Bunday holda, biz motorni ikkala yo'nalishda ham ishlatishimiz kerak bu faqat oldinga/teskari boshqaruv relesi sxemasi yoki mantiq orqali mumkin. Bu erda biz PLCda oddiy oldinga/teskari boshqaruv mantiqidan foydalanib, bu muammoni hal qilamiz. Biz dvigatelni boshqarish uchun ikkita kontaktor olamiz. Oldinga yo'nalishni boshqarish uchun birinchi kontaktor va dvigatelning teskari yo'nalishini boshqarish uchun ikkinchi kontaktordan foydalanamiz. Bundan tashqari, dvigatelning oldinga, teskari va to'xtash funksiyalari uchun uchta tugmachani ko'rib chiqishimiz kerak. Shunday qilib, bu erda operator oldinga ishlash uchun FWD PB, teskari ishlash uchun REV PB va to'xtatish funksiyasi uchun STOP PB dan foydalanadi.

PLC chiqishlari ro'yxati

Dvigatel oldinga: Q0.0

Dvigatel teskari: Q0.1

Dvigatelni oldinga/teskari boshqarish uchun PLC narvon diagrammasi

PLC narvon diagrammasining mantiqiy tavsifi

Ushbu ilovada biz dasturlash uchun Siemens S7-1200 PLC va TIA Portal dasturidan foydalanamiz.. Biz 1-tarmoqdagi oldinga siljish holati uchun mantiqni yozamiz. Bu erda dvigatelning oldinga ishlashi uchun FWD PB (I0.0) ning YO'Q kontaktidan foydalanamiz shuning uchun dvigatelning oldinga chiqish bobinining bitta YO'Q kontaktidan foydalanishimiz kerak. (Q0.0) qulflash uchun. (Bosish tugmasi faqat bir lahzalik aloqani ta'minlaydi va biz harakatni mahkamlashimiz kerak, shunda motor oldinga siljish kontaktidan foydalaniladi). Dvigatelning teskari chiqishining (Q0.1) NC kontaktini zanjirni ochish uchun ketma-ket joylashtirilgandan so'ng oldinga va orqaga bir vaqtning o'zida ishlamasligi kerak. Endi 2-tarmoqdagi teskari holat uchun mantiqni yozib bu erdagi dvigatelning teskari funktsiyasi uchun REV PB (I0.2) ning NO kontaktini olamiz, shuningdek, dvigatelning teskari chiqish lasanining (Q0.1) yana bitta kontaktini olamiz vosita teskari chiqishi (Q0.1). (Bosish tugmasi faqat bir lahzalik aloqani ta'minlaydi va biz harakatni mahkamlashimiz kerak, shunda motor oldinga siljish kontaktidan foydalaniladi) shuningde , kontaktlarning zanglashiga olib kirish uchun dvigatelning oldinga chiqish bobini (Q0.0) ketma-ket qo'ying, chunki oldinga va orqaga bir vaqtning o'zida ishlamasligi kerak. Qulflash maqsadida FWD PB (I0.0) ning NC kontaktini REV PB (I0.2) bilan ketma-ket joylashtiring va REV PB (I0.2) ning NC kontaktini FWD PB (I0.0) bilan ketma-ket joylashtiring. NC Kontaktini ikkala tarmoqqa ketma-ket joylashtiring, shunda operator STOP PB tugmasini bosib oldinga yoki teskari aylanishni to'xtata oladi. Bu erda biz motorni himoya qilish uchun OLR dan foydalandik , shuning uchun motorni himoya qilish uchun ikkala tarmoqqa ketma-ket Dvigatel safarining NC kontaktini (I0.3) qo'shing.

Uch fazali asenxron dvigatelni boshqarish uchun PLC dasturi va ish vaqtining sinov holatlari.

Kirish signal	Chiqish signal	Vazifasi
I 0.0=1	Q 0.0=1	Dvegatelni oldinga aylantirish
I 0.1=0	Q 0.1=1	Dvegatelni orqaga aylantirish
I 0.2=1	Q0.1*Q0.1=0	Dvegatelni to'xtatish
I 0.3=1	Q0.1*Q0.1=0	Dvegatelni to'xtatish

Taqdiqot ishi nasos agregatlarini avtomatlashtirishda inson-mashina interfeysini tashkil etish masalasini ko'rib chiqishga bag'ishlangan. Jarayonni amalga oshirish uchun eng ommabop va ish samaradorligi yuqori bo'lgan Siemens S7-1200 PLC va TIA Portal dasturidan foydalanildi. Bu orqali nasos agregatini boshqarish jarayonini avtomatlashtirish amalga oshirildi.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI.

1. Isroilovich, U. J. (2022). Kremniy Tagliklari Asosida Gaas Li Quyosh Elementlari Olish Texnologiyasini Yaratish Omillari. International Journal of Formal Education, 1(8), 43-48.
2. Усмонов, Ж. И. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ И ВЫБОР СТРУКТУРЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ ФОТОПРЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЕЙ. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 13, 179-185.
3. Isroilovich, U. J. (2022). GAAS EPITAKSIAL QATLAMLARNING SUV BUG'REAKSIASI BILAN O'STIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TADQIQ QILISH. Uzbek Scholar Journal, 10, 380-387.

4. Усманов, Ж. И., & Абдуллаев, М. Ш. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПОЛУПРОВОДНИКОВЫХ УСТРОЙСТВ. *Universum: технические науки*, (4-10 (97)), 37-40.
5. Усманов, Ж. И. (2021). Исследование влияния положения уровня ферми на фотопроводимость монокристаллического кремния Si< B, MN> с. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 494-498.
6. Usmonov J.I. SPECTRAL DEPENDENCE OF THE PHOTOCONDUCTIVITY OF SINGLE-CRYSTAL SILICON ON THE POSITION OF THE FERMI LEVEL // *The Way of Science*, 2020. № 3 (73).
7. Usmonov J.I. DEVELOPMENT OF DEVICES BASED ON SILICON WITH MANGANESE NANOCLUSTERS WITH THE PROPERTIES OF AVALANCHE FLIGHT DIODES // *International scientific conference, Uzbekistan*.
8. Usmonov J.I. Development of photocells for generation of sub-band photocarriers // 25th International Scientific and Practical Conference «INNOVATION-2021», Uzbekistan.
9. Усмонов, Ж. И. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕДУР ВЫРАЩИВАНИЯ ИЗОТИПНЫХ ГЕТЕРОЭПИТАКСИАЛЬНЫХ ПЕРЕХОДОВ AlGaAs-GaAs и InGaAs/GaAs. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 33, 381-386.
10. T. G. Abdukarimov, Sh. N. Erkinov, Arrangement of equipment at production site of multi-product production using heuristic algorithm E3S *Web of Conferences* 401, 05015 (2023) CONMECHYDRO – 2023 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202340105015>
11. Tojiddin Juraev a), Shavkat Imomov b), Dilorom Ubaydullayeva c), Tulkin Abdukarimov Constructive Geometric Modeling the Double Sided Moldboard Bodies for Bidirectional Rotary Plows *Proceedings of the III International Conference on Advances in Science, Engineering, and Digital Education AIP Conf. Proc.* 2969, 030018-1–030018-4; <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0181766>
12. V.P.Voronenko T.G.Abdukarimov. Расстановка оборудования на производственном участке многономенклатурного производства с использованием эвристического алгоритма <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44370400>
13. A.E. Boboyorov. F.N. Abdurashidov. SOFTWARE ANALYSIS OF AN AUTOMATED HYDROPONICS SYSTEM. *International Journal on Integrated Education*(2023). <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE>
14. A.E. Boboyorov. H.N. To'xtayev. D.H. Olimov. Artezian tik quduqlarida nasoslarini boshqarish va avtomatlashtirishni PLC dasturiy ta'minot tizimini ishlab chiqish. «*JOURNAL OF UNIVERSAL SCIENCE RESEARCH*» ilmiy jurnali(2023). 1(12), 239–245. Retrieved from
15. A.E. Boboyorov. J.V. Aliyev. Sh.E. Xolmuminov. KIYIMLARGALAZERLIISHLOVBERISHTEXNALOGIYASITAXLILI. <<INTERNATIONALJOURNALOFSCIENTIFICRESEARCHERS>> (2023) Volume2,Issue2,2023. <https://wordlyknowledge.uz/index.php/IJSR/article/view/3087/4643>
16. Mirziyoev, Shavkat Miromonovich. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. - Toshkent: «O'zbekiston», 2016.
17. Mirziyoev, Shavkat Miromonovich. Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash – yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligining garovi. 2016 yil 7 dekabr /Sh.M.Mirziyoev. – Toshkent : “O'zbekiston”, 2017.
18. Абдуллаев М. Ш., Йўлдошев С., Рўзибоев Ш. АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ ПРОЦЕССА ПОЛИВА АМАРАНТА В НЕБОЛЬШИХ ХОЗЯЙСТВАХ // *Экономика и социум*. – 2021. – №. 3-1. – С. 370-373.
19. Pulotova M. R., Abdullayev M. S. The use of black box method in automation of drying process of feed granules on the basis of amaranth // *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 1011-1018.
20. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ADVANTAGES OF DJANGO

21. FEMWORKER. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
22. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.
23. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.
24. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.
25. Садир Нематович Шодиев¹, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев². (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145–151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>
26. Usarov, Jabbor E; Eshnaev, Nortoji J; Khakimov, Jamshid O; Saidova, Dilobar I; Ikrom Sh Inoyatov; и другие. *NeuroQuantology; Bornova Izmir Том 20, Изд. 16, (2022): 4614 - 4622. DOI:10.48047/NQ.2022.20.16.NQ880468* <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/social-significance-creating-mechanism/docview/2816741596/se-2>
27. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In *Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве* (pp. 198-200).
28. J.Sh.Fazliyev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
29. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
30. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. *The Way of Science*, 56.
31. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 945–950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
32. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 938–944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>
33. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. *Интернаука. Science Journal*, 7(11).
34. Фазлиев, Ж.Ш.(2017).Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. *Интернаука*,(7-3),71-73.
35. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
36. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.

37. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
38. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. IMRAS, 7(2), 34-38.
39. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(8), 30-32.
40. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. Экономика и социум, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
41. AZ, S. Z. S. N. S. (2020). Analysis of the work on improving the design of dryers inside the ginning plants and the mode of drying.
42. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. E Conference Zone, 61–69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
43. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy yaylovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In «Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция (pp. 25-26).
44. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF THE MESH SURFACE ON THE SEED COTTON DURING THE SEPARATION OF COTTON FROM THE AIR STREAM. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 121-122).
45. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). KEY FACTORS FOR INCLUSION IN THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN IN THE CXM SEPARATOR AND THEIR IDENTIFICATION. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 119-121).
46. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).
47. Xudayev, I. J., Fazliev, J. S., & Ayusupova, A. (2021, October). Water saving up-to-date irrigation technologies. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 868, No. 1, p. 012040). IOP Publishing.
48. Ismoil, K., Jamoliddin, F., & Giyos, H. (2020). Water supply equipment and technology for irrigation in difficult conditions of desert-steppe zones. Journal of critical reviews, 7(11), 3102-3106.
49. Худайев, И. Ж., Фазлиев, Ж., & Хамзаев, Г. (2020). ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ВОДОБЕСПЕЧЕННОСТИ ЗЕМЕЛЬ ЗА СЧЕТ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ КОЛЛЕКТОРНО-ДРЕНАЖНЫХ ВОД. Universum: технические науки, (11-3 (80)), 5-7.
50. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Баратов, С. С. (2014). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГЛИНИСТОЙ ВОДЫ ПРИ КАПЕЛЬНОМ ОРОШЕНИИ. The Way of Science, (4), 77.
51. Худаев, И., & Фазлиев, Ж. (2022). Совершенствование водосберегающей технологии орошения в предгорных районах на юге республики Узбекистан.
52. KHUDAEV, I., & FAZLIEV, J. (2022). MODERN INNOVATIONS, SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Учредители: ООО" Сибирский Научный Центр ДНИТ", 2(2), 301-309.